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**16th Annual Scientific Conference of Montenegrin Sports Academy
“Sport, Physical Activity and Health: Contemporary Perspectives”**

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Edited by:

Bjelica, D., Popovic, S., Akpinar, S.

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and graphs. T-test for independent samples or a two-way chi-square were used to compare the differences between sexes. Prior to the processing of the data we set the level of risk at 5 %. Results: Data analysis found that MS primarily affects more women than men, 27.5 % of respondents were men and 72.5 % were women. The average age of respondents was 47.7 years. 53.75 % of respondents, which equals 43 patients, were engaged in activities of medium intensity, that slightly increase the respiratory and heart rate. The results show no statistically significant difference between genders in the daily amount of time and the amount of days per week spent performing medium-intensity activities. The study showed that on average, patients spend 6.05 hours sitting. A difference between genders in the amount of time spent sitting has been statistically proven – on average, men spend more time sitting than women. The preferred form of activity among most respondents is walking or swimming. Exactly half of respondents consider chores and household activities as physical activity with no statistically relevant difference between genders. Most respondents tolerate physical activity either fairly well or badly. Most common unpleasant body reactions, detected during physical activity or after it, were tingling, dizziness and fatigue. Most respondents also think that the disease limits their daily lives and daily activities, hence limiting their engagement in sports activities. 86.25 % of patients also think that proper physical exercise helps them alleviate some of the symptoms that accompany MS. Discussion: The results of our research can help us draw up a training program for patients with multiple sclerosis. They can also help us in creating an awareness brochure and informing patients about positive effects of physical activity. Results will be forwarded to the Association of Multiple Sclerosis of Slovenia, which will gain insight into the current attitude of their members toward physical activity and other factors associated with it. References: None.

DIVING-RELATED CHANGES IN FLOW-MEDIATED DILATION

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Introduction: Endothelial dysfunction is considered to be one of the most prominent reasons of decompression sickness – one among the most frequent complications related to SCUBA diving. Vascular endothelial function can be determined by a non-invasive method, estimating the arterial flow-mediated dilation (FMD). Consequently, the aim of the study was to compare the values of FMD pre- and post-dive, determining the diving-induced changes in the function of the vascular endothelium. Methods: Twelve male divers were recruited for this study, who performed a single-dive at a depth of 18 m with a 47-min bottom time and two-minute ascent to surface without any decompression stops. Endothelium-dependent vasodilator function of the brachial artery was assessed pre- and post-dive using a rapid inflation and deflation blood pressure cuff and a vascular ultrasound system with the belonging computer software. The measurements included the baseline diameter, peak diameter, time to peak diameter, shear rate and the absolute and relative values of FMD. Results: As a result of the study statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) changes were observed in the absolute and relative values of FMD pre-dive vs. post-dive towards the decrease of these values, paralleled with the same changes in shear rate. Post-dive baseline diameter, peak diameter and time to peak showed no statistically remarkable changes ($p \geq 0.05$). Discussion: We can conclude that there are significant changes in the vascular endothelial function related to SCUBA diving, and we suppose that these modifications are the result of cumulative effects of different diving-related factors, first of all hyperoxic and hyperbaric conditions, which lead to the damage of the endothelial function, presumably by modifying the bioavailability of nitrogen-monoxide (Yang et al., 2015; Thom et al., 2015). References: Yang M, Barak OF, Dujic Z, Madden D, Bhopale VM, Bhullar J, Thom SR

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Training and Testing

PRE-SEASON STRENGTH CHARACTERISTICS OF PROFESSIONAL SOCCER PLAYERS AND RELATIONSHIP WITH INJURY OF LOWER LIMB IN THE SEASON

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Introduction: The aim of study was to identify relationship between pre-season isokinetic strength and injuries of lower extremities throw to season in professional adult soccer players. In fact, the lack of strength of the quadriceps muscle is often a hidden culprit for such injuries (Hart, Pietrosimone, Hertel & Ingersoll, 2010). Hamstring are active knee stabilizers and if hamstrings are weak or do not function properly, the athlete is exposed to a greater risk of ACL transmission. Several studies have revealed a correlation between the strength of quadriceps and hamstring and the increased risk of injuries to the lower limbs (Croisier, Ganteaume, Binet, Genty & Ferret, 2008). Other studies, however, present an insignificant association of weak thigh muscles and the risk of injury (Engebretsen, Myklebust, Holme, Engebretsen & Bahr, 2010). **Material and method:** The strength characteristics in the senior category were observed in 227 healthy soccer players playing in the highest league competition in the Czech Republic. Tests of strength (flexors and knee extensions) were performed before the 2017/2018 season. Isokinetic strength parameters were monitored using an isokinetic dynamometer (Cybex Humac Norm®, USA). Retrospectively we compared the injury to pre-seasonal strength imbalances. **Results:** For the dominant leg at an angle of 60°/s for uninjured players, the mean H:Q ratio was $61.0 \pm 9.63\%$. Paradoxically injured players were at higher average values. For ACL injuries, players had an average ratio of flexors to knee extensions of $64.1 \pm 8.29\%$, $63.2 \pm 8.85\%$ for menisci injuries, and $61.4 \pm 10.3\%$ for ankle injuries. We can see a lower ratio only for other injuries (55.9 ± 6.90). In the non-dominant leg at a 60° angle, we observe the same effect as the lower limb of the dominant. **Discussions and conclusions:** Results show higher H: Q ratios in injured players compared to non-injured players in pre-season testing, suggesting that the low strength of the knee extensors may indicate a probability of lower limb injury in the season. **References:** Croisier, J.-L., Ganteaume, S., Binet, J., Genty, M., & Ferret, J.-M. (2008). Strength imbalances and prevention of hamstring injury in professional soccer players: a prospective study. *The American journal of sports medicine*, 36(8). Engebretsen, A. H., Myklebust, G., Holme, I., Engebretsen, L., & Bahr, R. (2010). Intrinsic risk factors for hamstring injuries among male soccer players: a prospective cohort study. *The American journal of sports medicine*, 38(6). Hart, J. M., Pietrosimone, B., Hertel, J., & Ingersoll, C. D. (2010). Quadriceps Activation Following Knee Injuries: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Athletic Training*, 45(1).